

Study on Factors Associated with Substance Use Among Undergraduate Students

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Abstract

The research work focused on study factor associated with substance use among undergraduate students. The study employed self-administered questionnaires to collect data which was analyzed and modelled using binary logistic approach. The logistic regression model was statistically significant, $\chi^2_{(27)} = 144.006$, $p < 0.05$. The model explained about 13.3% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in participants' response to substance use/drug abuse and correctly classified 67.0% of cases. Females were 1.51 times more likely to use substance or abuse drug than males. The odds ratio (1.431) of single was associated with an increased likelihood of substance use or abuse drug than married or divorced/separated. Starting substance use from secondary school stage was 1.018 times more likely than higher institution and participants from the rural area was associated with a reduction in the likelihood of substance use or abuse drug than those from urban centers.

Keywords: Undergraduate student, Substance use, Factor, Logistics regression.

Introduction

The current trend of substance abuse among youth is a major national concern, it is troubling, it has derogatory effects on youth such as health and behavioral problems, or even death. Falco (1988); as cited by Sambo (2008) viewed that "chronic use of substance can cause serious, sometimes irreversible damage to adolescents' physical and psychological development. Therefore, the issue of substance abuse has become a worrisome phenomenon, because youth are dying morally, socially, psychologically and physically. Currently, drugs ranging from alcohol, cigarettes, marijuana, cocaine, heroin to hashish and many others are readily available to youth in Nigeria and this has made many youths to be perpetrators of social vices in the society.

Substance use is an important public health concern in many countries across the globe. Among the general public, institutions of higher learning have developed a reputation for inducing new substance use among students. In addition to socio-demographic factors, substance use and abuse among university students often appear to be related to psychological stressors typically related to the demand to adapt to the new environment and the pressures associated with academia (Blows & Isaacs, 2022). In addition to reporting novice use, studies have also found that students who had prior exposure to substance use increased their frequency once exposed to the university environment (Arria et al., 2013; Jafari et al., 2011). A growing body of research has also shown

that university students reported using a number of substances at a greater rate than their non-student peers (Schulenberg et al., 2017; Dawson et al., 2004; Schulenberg & Patrick, 2012; National Institute on Drug Abuse (2017) & Center for Behavioral Health Statistics and Quality, 2019). Findings of such studies show that the use of alcohol, particularly getting drunk and binge drinking (Schulenberg et al., 2017; Dawson et al., 2004), marijuana (Schulenberg et al., 2017) and non-prescription amphetamine, were considerably higher among university students when compared with their non-university attending peers (Schulenberg et al., 2017; Schulenberg & Patrick, 2012; National Institute on Drug Abuse(2017) & Center for Behavioral Health Statistics and Quality, 2019).

The increasing rate of substance use among students in tertiary institutions is alarming and has become a critical public health concern in Nigeria. Nigeria, like many other developing nations, is currently facing a significant challenge with drug and substance abuse among youth. Tertiary institutions have become hotspots for such behaviors due to the combination of academic pressure, social experimentation, peer influence, and a lack of effective control systems. While the government and non-governmental organizations have made efforts to combat the menace, the trend continues to grow, and new substances are constantly introduced. In view of the above, this study aimed to examine the effect some socio demographic factors associated with substance use among undergraduate students using Kwara State Polytechnic, Ilorin as a case study.

Literature review

Substance use among university students is a growing public health concern, influenced by factors such as peer pressure, academic stress, and socioeconomic status. Eneh & Stanley (2004) reported high tobacco and alcohol use among university students in Port Harcourt. Talaei et al. (2008) further highlight the prevalence of substance use among university students in Iran. Their study at Azad University of Torbat Jaam found that 30.7% of students reported a lifetime history of substance use, with significantly higher rates among male students (78.8%) compared to females (21.2%). Cigarettes were the most commonly used substance (19.2%), followed by opium (15.4%) and alcohol (10.8%). The study also reported that 14.9% of students had used substances in the past month and 15.1% in the past year. Peer influence remains a significant determinant of substance use among students. Cicognani & Zani (2011) emphasized the role of peer networks in shaping substance use tendencies. Talaei et al. (2008) corroborated this, identifying peer pressure as the most commonly cited reason for substance use among university students. Other reasons included emotional distress, unemployment, and family issues. Duru et al. (2017) showed that gender and peer pressure were strong predictors of drug use. Adekeye et al. (2015) found that over 35% of undergraduates in South-West Nigeria had used psychoactive substances at least once. Previous research has consistently classified university students as a high-risk group for substance use. A study by Aguocha & Nwefoh (2021) found that the lifetime prevalence of psychoactive substance use among undergraduates in Nigeria was 84.5%, with alcohol having the highest usage rate (82.7% lifetime and 61.1% in the past 12 months). Similarly, Okoro and Chikezie (2024) found that among medical students at Niger Delta University, the lifetime prevalence of alcohol use was 14.8%, while 9.9% had used psychoactive substances. Weni (2024), findings indicate that

alcohol is the most commonly used substance, with a prevalence of 67.8%, followed by tobacco (36.4%) and cannabis (29.6%). Male students exhibit higher substance use rates than females across all categories. Students aged 22–27 show the highest prevalence, suggesting increased substance experimentation in older cohorts. According to faculty-specific trends, the Faculty of Management Sciences is the group that uses drugs the most, which may be due to particular social dynamics or stressors facing the faculty.

Methodology

The study was cross-sectional, and the study population included undergraduate students within the main campus of Kwara State Polytechnic, Ilorin. As this study assessed the effect of some demographic characteristics on substance use. The sample size was determined using Fisher’s formula, $n = Z^2pq/d^2$ where n = minimum sample size; p = population proportion; $q = 1-p$; d = margin of error; Z = standard normal deviate at 95%. A structured, self-administered questionnaire was used for data collection. A pre-test to determine the reliability of the instrument was conducted among 50 undergraduates who were not part of the sampling for the study. Binary logistic regression was used to identify predictors of substance use. The level of significance was set at p value of less than 0.05.

Data analysis and results

Table 1. Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients

		Chi-square	df	Sig.(p-value)
Step 1	Step	144.006	27	0.000
	Block	144.006	27	0.000
	Model	144.006	27	0.000

From Table 1, the model was statistically significant when compared to the null model, $\chi^2_{(27)} = 144.006, p\text{-value} < 0.05$.

Table 2. Model Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	1706.750 ^a	0.097	0.133
a. Estimation terminated at iteration number 5 because parameter estimates changed by less than .001.			

From Table 2, the ‘pseudo R^2 ’ values which is Nagelkerke R Square value is 0.133 or 13.3% of the variation in participants response to substance use can be explained by the full model suggesting that predictions are fairly reliable.

Table 3. Hosmer and Lemeshow Test

Step	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1	6.904	8	0.547

Table 3 *p*-values greater than 0.05 indicate a well-fitted model, we rejects the null hypothesis that the observed and predicted probabilities are the same.

Table 4. Coefficients of the Model

Variable	B	S.E.	Wald	df	<i>p</i> -value	Exp(B) [Odd ratio]
Aggregate Factor	-0.437	0.119	13.411	1	0.000*	0.646
Effect of substance use	-0.175	0.118	2.221	1	0.136	0.839
Age group			3.264	3	0.353	
Under 18 years	-0.322	0.231	1.949	1	0.163	0.725
18-24 years	-0.293	0.213	1.886	1	0.170	0.746
25-30 years	-0.406	0.229	3.153	1	0.076	0.666
30+ years (Referent)						
Gender (Female)	0.412	0.121	11.548	1	0.001*	1.51
Male (Referent)						
Level			10.65	3	0.014*	
ND1	0.417	0.188	4.92	1	0.027*	1.517
ND2	0.504	0.178	8.045	1	0.005*	1.655
HND1	0.097	0.186	0.272	1	0.602	1.102
HND2 (Referent)						
Institute			21.617	4	0.000*	
IAS	-0.088	0.288	0.093	1	0.761	0.916
IOT	-0.012	0.3	0.002	1	0.968	0.988
IFMS	-0.58	0.261	4.928	1	0.026*	0.56
IICT	-0.732	0.276	7.04	1	0.008*	0.481
IES(Referent)						
Marital Status			8.152	2	0.017*	
Single	0.359	0.338	1.126	1	0.289	1.431
Married	-0.048	0.355	0.018	1	0.893	0.953
Divorced/Separated(Referent)						
Place of residence (Rural)	-0.103	0.132	0.603	1	0.438	0.902
Urban(Referent)						
School level when started substance use			0.734	2	0.693	
Primary	-0.174	0.214	0.658	1	0.417	0.841
Secondary	0.018	0.136	0.018	1	0.894	1.018

Higher Institution(Referent)						
Parent/Guidance education level			8.403	2	0.015*	
Primary	-0.471	0.166	8.087	1	0.004*	0.625
Secondary	-0.098	0.135	0.525	1	0.469	0.907
Graduate(Referent)						
Types of substance use			28.97	7	0.000*	
Medication	-0.802	0.295	7.414	1	0.006*	0.448
Alcohol	-0.807	0.289	7.784	1	0.005*	0.446
Tobacco	-1.111	0.37	9.029	1	0.003*	0.329
Cannabis	0.13	0.385	0.113	1	0.736	1.138
Methamphetamine	-0.326	0.477	0.467	1	0.494	0.721
Tramadol	-0.131	0.387	0.115	1	0.735	0.877
Cocaine/Heroin	0.728	0.818	0.792	1	0.373	2.071
Others(Referent)						
Constant	3.754	0.677	30.781	1	0.000*	42.687

* p -value < 0.05 is significant

From Table 4, aggregate factor, gender and marital status were significant as a whole. The participants' level is significant as whole and ND1 or ND2 compare to HND1 or HND2. Institute of the students is significant as whole and IFMS or ICT compare IAS or IOT or IES. Parent/guidance education level is significant as whole and primary education row compare secondary school or higher institution. Also, the types of substance use is significant as whole and medication or alcohol or tobacco compare to others. The effect, age group, place of residence as well as school level when started substance use were not significant to the model. For significant results, the odds of substance use for gender was 1.51 times the odds for male. The odds of substance use for ND2 students 1.655 times the odds for the HND2 participant. On the marital status the odds of substance use for single was 1.431 times the odds for divorced/separated. The odds of substance use for the parent/guidance with primary level of education was 0.625 times the odds for the parent/guidance who are graduates. Lastly, participants' odds of substance use for medication (0.448), alcohol (0.446) and tobacco (0.329), respectively times for sub

Table 5. Classification Table

Observed		Predicted		
		Substance use or drug abuse		Percentage Correct
		Yes	No	
Substance use or drug abuse	Yes	288	222	56.5
	No	245	661	73
Overall Percentage				67

Table 5 output result summarizes the observed group and the predicted group classification. The proportion of actual positives that are correctly identified by the model was 56.5% while the

proportion of actual negatives that are correctly identified by the model was 73.0%. The overall correctly specified group percentage is 67.0% (Accuracy).

Conclusion

A logistic regression was carried out to assess the effect of some selected socio demographic characteristics on the likelihood of substance use or drug abuse among the undergraduate students. The overall model was statistically significant when compared to the null model, ($\chi^2_{(27)} = 144.006$, p -value < 0.05), explained about 13.3% of the variation of participants' response (Nagelkerke R^2) and correctly predicted 67.0% of cases. Aggregate factor ($p = 0.000$), gender ($p = 0.001$), level ($p = 0.014$), institute ($p = 0.000$), marital status ($p = 0.017$), parent/guidance level of education ($p = 0.015$) and types of substance use ($p = 0.000$) were statistically significant to the model but effect substance use ($p = 0.136$), age group ($p = 0.353$), place of residence ($p = 0.438$) and participants' school level when started substance use ($p = 0.693$) were not.

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